

Hypothalamic Atrophy as a Probable Neuroprodrome to Autism: A Short Review

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Abstract

Among the many neurodevelopmental disorders, the autism spectrum disorder (or autism for short) represents a daunting challenge for psychiatry, neuroscience and special education (including educational therapy) because of its high prevalence worldwide, prevailing phenomenon (or possibly even noumenon?), complicatedness as well as considerable heterogeneity. As such, facing with so many obstacles and gaps in the current knowledge and understanding of the autistic condition, Di Martino et al. (2014) argued strongly that “it certainly requires large-scale multidisciplinary efforts” (p. 659). For these reasons, despite the field of genetics having pioneered data sharing, neuroimaging had failed to keep up its pace. In this brief review, the main focus is targeted at only one specific area of the brain – hypothalamus – and the impact of two of its hormones – oxytocin (OXT) and arginine vasopressin (AVP) – on autism.

Key Words: Autism, Hypothalamic Atrophy, Hypothalamus, Oxytocin, Vasopressin

Introduction

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD; hereafter, autism) is one of the most heritable neurodevelopmental disorder (NDD) with an early onset, with its typical symptoms being observed in the first three years of life in order to meet criteria for the triad of impairments or ‘core’ symptoms, i.e., difficulties with social interaction and communication, and by restricted and repetitive behavior, in its nosological classification system. “As such, the focus on identifying a prodrome over the past 20 years has been on pre-clinical signs or indicators that will be present very early in life, certainly in infancy” (Yirmiya & Charman, 2010, p. 432). A number of novel lines of investigation have been used to this end, including retrospective coding of home videos, prospective population screening and high-risk sibling studies; as well as the investigation of pre- and peri-natal, brain developmental and other biological factors. While no single prodromal sign is expected to be present in all cases, a picture is emerging of indicative prodromal signs in infancy and initial studies are being undertaken to attempt to ameliorate early presentation and even ‘prevent’ emergence of the full syndrome (Yirmiya & Charman, 2010, p. 432)

The Hypothalamus

Though a small region of the forebrain in comparison with the rest of the brain, the hypothalamus is located below and in between the pituitary gland (see Figure 1) and the thalamus, which coordinates both the autonomic nervous

system and the activity of the pituitary gland. The hypothalamus plays a vital role in the production of many important hormones as well as in the stimulation of many essential processes in the body, such as modulation of the body temperature, thirst, hunger, and other homeostatic systems, and also involves in sleep and emotional activity.

Figure 1. The Location of Hypothalamus

The main function of the hypothalamus is to maintain homeostasis (e.g., glucose homeostasis), i.e., to keep our body in a stable, constant condition, and in other words, it means “a healthful, balanced bodily state” (Johnson, 2018, para. 4), or to establish a relatively stable equilibrium between interdependent elements, especially as maintained by physiological processes within our body, as much as possible.

As mentioned earlier, the hypothalamus responds to a wide range of internal bio-signals and external eco-signals (environment), such as body temperature, hunger and thirst, feelings of being full up after a meal, blood pressure (including hypertension and hypotension), and levels of hormones in the circulation. It also responds to stress and modulates our daily bodily rhythms (e.g., the night-time secretion of [melatonin](#) from the [pineal gland](#); the changes in the stress hormone known as cortisol; and regulation of our body temperature over a 24-hour period). Information collected and combined by the hypothalamus helps to put appropriate changes in place to correct any imbalances in our body. For instance, if a person feels thirsty or hungry, the brain will relay the information via the efferent neurons the need for more water or nutrients in order to achieve homeostasis.

The hypothalamus is like an intermediary between the endocrine system – a collection of ductless glands that produce hormones and secrete them into the circulatory system – and the central nervous system (CNS), which consists the brain, spinal cord, sensory organs and all the neurons to form a communication network between the various organs of the body, playing many essential bodily functions to achieve homeostasis, such as the following: appetite (hunger) and weight control, balancing bodily fluids, blood pressure and heart rhythm/rate, body temperature, childbirth, emotions and moods, production of digestive juices, sleep cycles, sex drive, and thirst.

When different parts of the body send their signals to the brain, they put the hypothalamus on alert, reporting any unbalanced factors that need to be addressed. The hypothalamus then responds quickly by releasing the right hormones into the bloodstream to balance the body. Imagine if the hypothalamus is malfunctioning as a result of

atrophy or agenesis/dysgenesis, it can result in many challenging somatic problems that lead to a wide range of rare disorders including autism. In fact, “[T]here is growing interest in understanding the specific brain regions underlying the association between metabolic changes and a range of neurodegenerative diseases” (Ahmed & Farooqi, 2017, p. 1006). In the hypothalamic atrophy on one hand, the small region of hypothalamus critical to the regulation of energy balance has become degenerated. This has been observed in Huntington’s Disease (Douaud et al., 2006; Kremer et al., 1990; Petersén & Björkqvist, 2006) and Fronto-Temporal Dementia (FTD) (Bocchetta et al., 2015; Jacobson & Marcus, 2008; Piguet et al., 2011). In the hypothalamic dysgenesis on the other hand, it is found that the corpus callosum fails to develop fully resulting in callosal agenesis – “a congenital brain anomaly caused by embryonal hypogenesis of the corpus callosum” (Imataka et al., 2006, p. 160), with epilepsy and motor disturbance also being observed in some of these cases.

Primary Hormones of Hypothalamus

The hypothalamus, being highly involved in the functions of pituitary gland (see Figure 2), which consists of pars tuberalis, pars distalis, pars nervosa and pars intermedia, is the most essential of the endocrine system. When it receives a signal from the CNS, the hypothalamus secretes neurohormones that start and/or halt the pituitary gland to secrete certain hormones to the rest of the endocrine system in order to ensure that the internal processes of the body are balanced and functioning properly as they should, i.e., maintaining homeostasis (Sargis, 2021).

Figure 2. Hypothalamus and Pituitary Gland

The primary hormones, which are bio-chemicals synthesized and produced by the endocrine glands to control and regulate the activity of certain cells and organs, secreted by the hypothalamus include anti-diuretic hormone (ADH), corticotropin-releasing hormone (CRH), growth hormone-releasing hormone (GHRH) or growth hormone-inhibiting hormone (GHIH), gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH), prolactin-releasing hormone (PRH) or prolactin-inhibiting hormone (PIH), and thyrotropin-releasing hormone (TRH). Each of these primary hormones is briefly discussed below.

ADH (also known as vasopressin), a neuro-secretory peptide hormone, plays an important role in regulating various physiological processes (e.g., prevention of the production of dilute urine, increased water absorption into the blood by kidneys) and several life-threatening conditions (e.g., bleeding abnormalities and septic shocks).

Recently, a study conducted by Joo et al. (2004) found that oxytocin (OXT) “has an antidiuretic effect and increases the urinary excretion of aquaporin-2 (AQP2) in humans whose urinary concentration mechanism is preserved. The results suggest that AQP2 might have a regulatory role in the antidiuretic action of OXT in humans” (p. 2480). The antidiuretic effect of OXT in humans remains controversial. “Urinary excretion of renal aquaporin-2 (AQP2) can be used as an index of the action of vasopressin on the kidney” (Joo et al., 2004, p. 2480).

CRH, which is also known as corticotropin-releasing factor (CRF) or corticoliberin, is secreted by the paraventricular nucleus (PVN) of the hypothalamus in response to stress. An increase in the CRH production has been found to associate with Alzheimer's Disease (AD) and major depression (see Raadsheer et al., 1995, for detail), and the autosomal recessive hypothalamic corticotropin deficiency has multiple and potentially fatal metabolic consequences including hypoglycemia (low sugar blood).

GHRH (also known as somatocinin) is a 44-amino acid peptide hormone that stimulates the synthesis and release of growth hormone (GH) in the pituitary gland. It is produced in the arcuate nucleus of the hypothalamus. Opposite of GHRH is the growth hormone-inhibiting hormone (GHIH). Its primary role is to prevent the production of other hormones as well as to stop the unnatural rapid reproduction of cells, such as those with excessive somatostatin levels resulting in a specific type of endocrine tumor known as somatostatinoma. In the extreme suppression of the hormones normally inhibited by somatostatin (e.g., insulin), it can lead to major health problems. In addition, somatostatin also acts as a neurotransmitter and has a role in the gastrointestinal tract, i.e., it reduces gastric secretion as well as emits gastrointestinal hormones (e.g., secretin and gastrin).

GnRH, a tropic peptide hormone synthesized and released from GnRH neurons within the hypothalamus, is responsible for the release of (i) follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), which regulates the development, growth, pubertal maturation, and reproductive processes of the body; and (ii) luteinizing hormone (LH), which triggers ovulation (Nosek, 1998) and development of the corpus luteum in females, and stimulates Leydig cell production of testosterone in males (Nosek, 1998). LH is called interstitial cell–stimulating hormone (ICSH) in males (Louvet, Harman, & Ross, 1975). Both FSH and LH from the anterior pituitary gland work together in the reproductive system (see Bowen, 2018, for detail).

Prolactin-releasing hormone (PRH) (also known as prolactin-inhibiting hormone (PIH) or dopamine) is produced in the arcuate nucleus and is released in the hypothalamo-hypophysial blood vessels that supply PRH to the pituitary gland to inhibit the production of prolactin. It is associated with reward-motivated behavior and motor control. Any dysfunction of the dopaminergic pathway can result in several neurological diseases, e.g., Parkinson's Disease “caused by the loss of dopamine-secreting neurons and it leads to motor impairment” (Conrad, 2018, para. 2). PRH prompts the anterior pituitary to stimulate breast milk production through the production of prolactin. Conversely, it also inhibits prolactin to stop milk production.

TRH is a hypophysiotropic hormone produced by neurons in the hypothalamus. Its role is to stimulate the release of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), which regulates metabolism, energy, and growth and development, and prolactin from the anterior pituitary gland. TRH has been used clinically for the treatment of spinocerebellar degeneration and disturbance of consciousness in humans. Moreover, TRH has anti-depressant and anti-suicidal properties (Marangell et al., 1997) and it has been used to develop TRH nasal spray used in the US Army to prevent suicide amongst its ranks.

The Neuropeptides: Oxytocin and Arginine Vasopressin

In the hypothalamus, “the ratio of vasopressin to oxytocin was approximately 3:1” (Jenkins et al., 1984, p. 111). In the extrahypothalamic areas of the brain, the greatest amount of both neuropeptides can be found in the locus coeruleus, and also, to a lesser extent, in the periaqueductal grey, too. The arginine vasopressin (AVP) “only was found in the substantia nigra, and globus pallidus” (Jenkins et al., 1984, p. 111). The amount of OXT being greater than AVP can be found in the medulla, which includes the nucleus of the solitary tract, the dorsal nucleus of the vagus, and the nucleus of the spinal tract of the trigeminal nerve. Additionally, OXT predominated over AVP to an even greater extent in the spinal cord, “and reached particularly high values in certain segments of the intermediolateral grey column and dorsal horn” (Jenkins et al., 1984, p. 111).

According to Benarroch (2013), OXT and arginine vasopressin (AVP) are two closely related neuropeptides that are known for their peripheral hormonal effects. However, OXT and AVP as well as their receptors are also expressed in several areas of the central nervous system (CNS) with widespread neuromodulatory effects on homeostasis and behavior. As a result, “OXT and AVP have been referred to as social neuropeptides as they have a highly conserved role as mediators of complex social cognition and interaction in both animals and humans” (Benarroch, 2013, p. 1521).

Oxytocin

Oxytocin (OXT) – a hormone produced in the hypothalamus and released by the pituitary gland – has been a subject of interest in relation to autism. The key reason is the influence of this hormone in social behaviors, especially in people on the autistic spectrum with social difficulties (e.g., social awareness, social recognition and social interaction or communication) and repetitive behavior. OXT has been described as the “love drug” as “it creates a sense of well-being, such as calmness, relaxation, and alleviating anxiety.” (Deolinda, 2021, para. 4). As OXT can reduce anxiety levels and reactivity to stressors, it acts as a good buffer to social stress. This, in turn, helps to alleviate repetitive behaviors observed in individuals with autism. According to Deolinda (2021), when the plasma OXT is low or lacking, OXT processing defects are manifested in the social impairment of individuals with (and/or without) autism, but more so in those with autism.

Apparently, it seems that there is some kind of association between OXT and autism, since OXT plays an essential role in developing social skills. Individuals with autism manifest social difficulties, which, in turn, trigger (social) anxiety in them. However, this “does not necessarily mean that lack of oxytocin is a cause” (Deolinda, 2021, para.

13). In fact, Deolinda (2021) explained that in both groups of individuals with autism and without autism, the lack of OXT in the brain can lead to an increase in anxiety and fear. This may explain why social ineptitude is often observed in children and adults with autism.

Vasopressin

The hormone vasopressin – also known as antidiuretic hormone (or ADH for short), arginine vasopressin (AVP), or argipressin – is a hormone synthesized as a peptide prohormone in neurons in the hypothalamus, and is converted to AVP. It is a small peptide that modulates several functions, such as blood pressure, water balance and thirst, and social behavior, such as social interaction and selection of mate in terms of preference and attachment (Hammock, 2019). Because of its effects on social behavior, the AVP system has been found to offer as a potential therapeutic treatment for easing social impairments in autism. In addition, it also “modulates territorial behaviors towards potential same-sex rivals, increases attraction, as well as sexual and reproductive behaviors” (Henderson, 2021, para. 8).

OXT/AVAP Systems

Both OXT and AVP are structurally homologous peptide hormones synthesized in the hypothalamus. Together, the general role of OXT/AVP systems are to modulate social behavior and emotions, but they also participate in cognitive functioning. Moreover, the recent study done by Abramova et al. (2020) has found the OXT/AVP systems to be involved in “the formation of social, working, spatial and episodic memory, mediated by such brain structures as the hippocampal CA2 and CA3 regions, amygdala and prefrontal cortex” (p. 1). Additionally, the stress-induced imbalance of the OXT/AVP systems can result in an increased risk of various mental disorders (e.g., autism, borderline personality disorder, depression, schizophrenia, and social anxiety disorder) with cognitive deficits also being observed in these disorders.

Hypothalamic Atrophy in Autism

Research studies on the hypothalamus and its atrophy in autism have been sporadic. According to Wolfe et al. (2015), the reason is twofold: firstly, it is due to the small size of hypothalamus; and secondly, there are methodological constraints in the current technology to study it. Despite the challenges, Wolfe et al. (2015) used the neuroimaging to examine the hypothalamic atrophy in individuals with autism in comparison to those who were typically-developing (TD) in the following way (p. 1017): Firstly, the grey matter (GM) density was directly measured by application of a region-of-interest (ROI) analysis in the Voxel-Based Morphometry (VBM), in a homogenous sample of participants controlled for age and IQ. Secondly, for generalization, the third ventricular volume – based on its position bilaterally surrounded by the hypothalamus, was measured by using Freesurfer (a brain imaging software package) in a heterogeneous sample of participants. The findings of Wolfe et al. (2015) showed a decrease in the hypothalamic GM density but an increased third ventricle volume in participants with autism compared to TD participants. Their results also provided neuroanatomical insights to socialization deficits in individuals with autism that might also be relevant for other psychotic disorders.

Interestingly, several neuroimaging studies (e.g., Callen et al., 2001; Ishii & Iadecola, 2015; Loskutova et al., 2010) that studied and observed hypothalamic atrophy in patients with Alzheimer's Disease (AD) have also found a decrease in the hypothalamic volume at the early clinical stages of AD in 10% and 12% in their respective cohorts (Callen et al., 2001; Loskutova et al., 2010). Although autism and AD are neurodevelopmental and neurodegenerative disorders respectively, with devastating effects, they share “the background of common associations like memory deficits, cognition changes, demyelination, oxidative stress and inflammation, an integral part of both disorders” (Khan et al., 2016, p. 390). Collectively, these factors contribute to the expression of autism and AD but the two disorders express at different stages of lifespan development involving certain susceptible genes, which is not within the scope of coverage in this paper.

Another interesting finding is that Amyloid Beta ($A\beta$ or Abeta), which denotes peptides of 36-43 amino acids, and whose normal function is still not well understood (Hiltunen, van Groen, & Jolkkonen, 2009), constitutes the main component of the amyloid plaques found in the brains of people with AD. Studies (e.g., Bailey et al., 2008; Sokol et al., 2006; Westmarket et al., 2011) have also linked this peptide to autism and related disorders such as Fragile-X Syndrome. According to Wright (2012), “[T]he researchers also found amyloid plaques in the brains of two individuals, aged 51 and 52, who had autism, and one individual aged 39 with the 15q duplication. This suggests that the enhanced levels of amyloid-beta in these individuals are a precursor to Alzheimer’s Disease” (para. 6).

Several other studies (e.g., Luo et al., 2003; Sadigh-Eteghad et al., 2014) conducted on animals have also suggested that the absence of $A\beta$ does not lead to any obvious loss of physiological function. Instead, several potential activities have been identified for $A\beta$: (i) activating kinase enzymes (Bogoyevitch et al., 2004; Tabaton et al., 2010), (ii) involving anti-microbial activity that is potentially associated with $A\beta$'s pro-inflammatory activity (Kagan et al., 2012; Li et al., 2018; Schluesener et al., 2012); (iii) functioning as a transcription factor (Bailey et al., 2011; Maloney, B., & Lahiri, 2011); (iv) protecting against oxidative stress (Baruch-Suchodolsky & Fischer, 2009; Zou et al., 2002); and (v) regulating cholesterol transport (Igbavboa et al., 2009; Yao & Papadopoulos, 2002).

Implications of Hypothalamic Atrophy in Autism Treatment

“OXT and AVP are emerging as targets for novel treatment approaches – particularly in synergistic combination with psychotherapy – for mental disorders characterized by social dysfunction, such as autism, social anxiety disorder, borderline personality disorder and schizophrenia” (Meyer-Lindenberg et al., 2011, p. 524).

According to Bartz and Hollander (2008) and Deolinda (2021), intravenous OXT administration (IOA) or OXT infusion therapy has been shown to promote trust and prosocial behavior, and, in turn, help to improve social learning and reduce repetitive behaviors in individuals with autism. It is available by prescription under the brand names Pitocin and Syntocinon. This is supported by the findings from a study done by Anagnostou et al. (2012): after a 6-week period of IOA, participants showed improved social cognition, reduced repetitive behaviors, relieve gastrointestinal discomfort, and improve emotional well-being for some of them. In terms of repetitive behaviors,

IOA did not impact on higher-order behaviors (e.g., compulsive-like behaviors) but more so on lower-order behaviors (e.g., self-stimulatory behavior). One possible explanation is that since the self-stimulatory behavior is a pleasurable act, OXT may replace that act due to its feel-good effect.

There are also vasopressin drugs under the brand names Pitressin and Vasopressin, but currently, they are not used in autism treatment, but for other medical conditions (e.g., asystole, diabetes insipidus and gastrointestinal hemorrhage). In one study based on efficacy findings in the VANILLA (Vasopressin ANtagonist to Improve social communication in Autism) done by Bolognani et al. (2019), it was revealed that blocking AVP with a pill called Balovaptan (developed by F. Hoffmann-La Roche AG – a Swiss multinational healthcare company that operates under Pharmaceuticals and Diagnostics divisions), which is a Vasopressin 1a (V1a) Receptor Antagonist (VRA) – an agent that interferes with action at the vasopressin receptors – with no known drug-related safety concerns identified to date, has shown to modestly improve social and communication skills in adults with autism. In fact, Keown (2018) reported that the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) called the drug a successful breakthrough for mediating and modulating key social behaviors in individuals with autism. In another study carried out by Parker et al. (2019), their findings suggested that delivering AVP via the nose increases social behavior scores in children with autism.

Concluding Remarks

More research is still needed to be done to understand diseases or disorders associated with the hypothalamus (also known as a hypothalamic disease/disorder), which include poor appetite, and sleep disorders (somnipathy) due to hypothalamic malfunctioning. Moreover, the hypothalamus and pituitary gland are so closely connected that it is often difficult to determine if a condition is linked to the hypothalamus or pituitary gland, especially hypothalamic-pituitary disorders. In fact, a physical injury to the head can impact the hypothalamus and it is one of the most common causes of hypothalamic dysfunction (Sargis, 2021).

While the exact root cause of autism continues to stay unknown, findings from recent research studies (Caria, Ciringione, & Falco, 2020; Chaminade et al., 2015; Wolfe et al., 2015) on the hypothalamus suggest that some form of hypothalamic disease may constitute a probable neuroprodrome (i.e., an early neurological symptom indicating the onset of a disease/illness) to autism could be caused by the atrophy of hypothalamus involving the OXT/AVP imbalance (Aoki et al., 2014; Baribeau & Anagnostou, 2015; Rutigliano et al., 2016). This discovery has added to the list of causality theories of autism, including environmental factors, exposure to pesticides and toxins, genetic factors and mutations, perinatal infections, mitochondrial dysfunction and social issues. In conclusion to this review, to put it succinctly, the causes of autism remain etiologically heterogeneous.

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